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Research article

Celsr3 is Required in Mouse Hippocampal Intrinsic Wiring and Spatial Learning

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Core tip:

We studied the *Celsr3|Emx1* mouse mutant model, in which *Celsr3* is selectively inactivated in hippocampal projection neurons. Inactivation of *Celsr3* in projection neurons perturbed intrinsic hippocampal wiring. Consistent with wiring defects, *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice showed impaired learning and memory, and were less anxiety-prone than control mice. Thus, *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice provide a simple way to study the consequences of defective hippocampal wiring in absence of drastic structural anomalies.

Abstract:

Background The atypical cadherin *Celsr3*, which belongs to the core planar cell polarity group, orchestrates axonal guidance and network wiring. Previous work using regional inactivation of *Celsr3* in forebrain showed that *Celsr3* is widely involved in hippocampal maturation and connectivity. However, inactivation in the whole forebrain does not provide sufficient specificity to address the function of *Celsr3* in detail.

Method We studied the *Celsr3|Emx1* mouse mutant model, in which *Celsr3* is selectively inactivated in hippocampal projection neurons, but not in entorhinal cortex, basal ganglia and interneurons.

Result In that mutant, the hippocampal cytoarchitecture was almost normal. Inactivation of *Celsr3* in projection neurons perturbed intrinsic hippocampal wiring. Consistent with wiring defects, *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice showed impaired learning and memory, and were less anxiety-prone than control mice.

Conclusion *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice provide a simple way to study the consequences of defective hippocampal wiring in absence of drastic structural anomalies.

Key words cell polarity; hippocampus; anxiety; *Emx1-Cre*.

INTRODUCTION

The hippocampal formation (HF) is crucial for learning and memory, and is also involved in emotion and cognition ¹. Interference with hippocampal wiring such as genetic ablation of entorhinal afferents, interruption of CA1—CA3 connections, or reduction of the hippocampal commissure, all cause learning and memory dysfunctions ²⁻⁵. Due to its important role, the HF has been implicated in several neurological disorders such as mood

disorders, especially major depressive disorder (MDD), Alzheimer's disease, transient global amnesia, temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE), schizophrenia, anxiety disorders or cognitive decline^{6,7}.

The HF is composed of the main following regions: dentate gyrus (DG), CA3, CA1, presubiculum and subiculum. Its anlage is laid on during embryonic development, and its architectonic development, wiring and maturation occur mostly postnatally^{8,9}. Inside the hippocampus, granule cells in the DG project to CA3 through the mossy fibers, and CA3 connects to CA1 by the Schaffer collaterals. Although the hippocampal network wiring diagram is well known, the mechanisms that control its development and maturation are not fully understood. The atypical seven transmembrane domain cadherin *Celsr3* belongs to the core planar cell polarity (PCP) group, which includes *Celsr1-3*, *Fzd3* and *6*, *Dvl1-3*, *Vangl1-2*, and *Prickle-like 1-4*¹⁰⁻¹². Among those proteins, *Celsr3* and *Fzd3* work together to orchestrate axonal guidance and brain wiring¹³⁻¹⁷. Previous work using regional inactivation of *Celsr3* in forebrain upon expression of *Foxg1-Cre* and *Dlx5/6-Cre* showed that *Celsr3* is widely involved in hippocampal maturation and connectivity². *Foxg1-Cre* inactivates *Celsr3* in all projection neurons and interneurons of the hippocampus, as well as in entorhinal cortex, septum and several other hippocampal afferents and projection targets¹⁸, and *Dlx5/6-Cre* is expressed in ganglionic eminences and therefore in basal telencephalon and in cortical and hippocampal interneurons¹⁹. Here, using *Emx1-Cre*, we probed the function of *Celsr3* following selective inactivation in hippocampal projection neurons²⁰. In this mutant model, we find that the hippocampal cytoarchitecture is almost normal. Lack of *Celsr3* in hippocampal projection neurons perturbs intrinsic wiring. Consistent with these wiring defects, *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice have impaired learning and memory, and are less anxiety-prone than control mice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

ANIMALS

All animal procedures were carried out according to guidelines and approved by the animal ethics committee of Jinan University. Mice generation and genotyping were described before (14). We used *Emx1-Cre; Celsr3f/-* (abbreviated as *Celsr3|Emx1*) as the experimental group, and *Emx1-Cre; Celsr3f/+* as the control group, to exclude phenotypes related to *Emx1-Cre*. Mice of either sex were used indiscriminately.

HISTOLOGY

For histological processing, P20 mice were anesthetized and perfused with a 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) solution in PBS. Brains were kept in the same fixative overnight at 4°C. 5µm thick paraffin coronal sections were prepared for Nissl staining. Preparations were examined and photographed with a Leica DM1000 microscope, and montages were edited with Photoshop (Adobe).

Mossy fibers were stained using the Neo-Timm stain²¹. Their density in CA3 was measured using Image J; the density of mossy fiber terminals in the stratum pyramidale or oriens in CA3 were ranked between 0 and 5 as described²². For tract tracing, DiI crystals were implanted in target areas of PFA fixed P14 brains using tungsten needles. A small crystal was inserted into entorhinal cortex and samples were incubated at 37 °C for 4 weeks. DiI implantation in CA1 was performed in vibratome sections, which were subsequently incubated at 37 °C for 1 week. Samples were sectioned in the coronal plane using a vibratome and sections were mounted in glycerol.

BEHAVIORAL STUDIES

Methods used in this work have been described previously² and are briefly summarized. For Morris Water Maze tests (MWM), a swimming pool was divided into four quadrants, with the escape platform hidden below the surface. All animals were pre-trained, and allowed to search for the platform for 180s, 4 trials (once from each quadrant). The Elevated Plus Maze (EPM)

apparatus included two open arms and two closed arms joined to a central platform. Mice were placed at the central platform and their movements were recorded for 5 min. Ten *Celsr3|Emx1* and eleven control mice, aged postnatal day (P) 20, were studied on three consecutive days (MWM) or tested once (EPM). Data were analyzed using EthoVision XT 7.0 (Noldus, The Netherlands).

STATISTICS

Results are expressed as mean \pm SEM. Area measurements and cell counting were done using Image J. The chi-square test was used to compare mossy fiber terminals. Data were analyzed using SPSS 17. $p < 0.05$ and <0.01 were considered significant and highly significant, respectively.

RESULTS

INACTIVATION OF *Celsr3* DOES NOT DISTURB HIPPOCAMPAL CYTOARCHITECTURE

In *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice, *Celsr3* is inactivated in *Emx1*-expressing projection neurons in the dorsal telencephalon, including hippocampal pyramidal cells and DG granule cells, from early embryonic stages²⁰. This results in absence of subcerebral projections such as the corticospinal tract (CST), while other components of the internal capsule such as thalamocortical and corticothalamic axons are preserved. *Celsr3|Emx1* mice are able to drink, eat, move and swim; they are fertile and can survive as long as control mice.

We studied the architecture of the hippocampus using Nissl-stained P20 coronal brain sections. In *Celsr3|Emx1* mice, the main regions of the hippocampal formation such as CA1, CA3 and DG formed normally (**Fig. 1A and B**).

INTRINSIC HIPPOCAMPAL WIRING IS DEFECTIVE IN *CELSR3|EMX1* MUTANT MICE

To assess whether *Celsr3* is essential for the intrinsic wiring of the hippocampal formation, we compared the local circuits in adult *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant and control mice. We studied mossy fiber projections using Timm's staining²³. In control animals, mossy fibers (MFs) reached their target territory in CA3 as two separate bundles, a main bundle (MB) and a smaller infrapyramidal bundle (IPB)²⁴. In *Celsr3|Emx1* mutants, although the MB was preserved, the IPB was blunted and failed to extend out of the hilus of the DG (Figure 1C and D). We also found that Timm-stained MFs terminals in the CA3 region were severely reduced, by about 4-fold in mutant versus control samples (**Fig. 1E-G**), clearly indicating a diminished MF projection in *Celsr3|Emx1* mutants.

Pyramidal cells in CA3 project to CA1. To visualize those connections, we implanted small Dil crystals in CA1 in coronal vibratome slices. In control mice, abundant fibers connecting CA1 and CA3 were labeled and many retrogradely labeled neurons were seen in CA3 (**Fig. 2A, C**). In contrast, very few fibers and cells could be seen upon tracer injection in slices from *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice (**Fig. 2B, D**), indicating that CA3—CA1 projections are defective in this mutant.

Those data show that the conditional inactivation of *Celsr3* in projection neurons is sufficient to perturb strongly intrinsic hippocampal wiring.

Figure 1 Mossy fiber projections are reduced in *Celsr3|Emx1* mice.

A-B: Hippocampal architecture is minimally affected in *Celsr3|Emx1* mice. Coronal sections from P20 brains stained with cresyl violet. In comparison to control mice (A), the mutant dorsal hippocampus looked slightly more globular (B) Ctx: cortex.

C-G: In P20 coronal sections, Timm staining (C-D) showed mossy fibers originating from the DG and extending to CA3, forming a main axon bundle (MB, arrowheads) and a smaller infrapyramidal bundle (IPB, arrows). Compared to control, the IPB was blunted and failed to extend out of the hilus of the DG in *Celsr3|Emx1* mice. Mossy fiber terminals in *Celsr3|Emx1* mice were significantly decreased compared to control mice (asterisks in E, F, quantification in G). E and F correspond to boxed areas in C and D. **: $p < 0.01$, $n=3$ in each group.

Figure 2 CA3—CA1 connections are altered by *Celsr3* inactivation.

Following implantation of small Dil crystals in CA1 in control slices (A, C), abundant labeled cell bodies were visualized in CA3, with fibers running between CA3 and CA1 (A, C). In the mutant (B, D) few cells (arrows and inset in D) were labeled in CA3 and no fibers, if any, were found running between CA1 and CA3. C and D correspond to insets in A, B. Ctx: cortex.

Figure 3 *Celsr3|Emx1* mice have behavioral deficits.

In the Morris Water Maze test (MWM), whereas control mice could find the platform after a short latency, mutant mice took longer (A). During the Elevated Plus Maze test (EPM), control mice mostly stayed in the closed arms, whereas mutant mice crossed closed and open arms repeatedly. *Celsr3|Emx1* mice spent a longer time in open arms than control mice (B). In the mutant, the number of times extending over arm edges was approximately four-fold that in the control (C). **: $p < 0.01$, $n=11$ in control group and $n=10$ in *Celsr3|Emx1* group.

***Celsr3|Emx1* MUTANT MICE HAVE IMPAIRED LEARNING AND MEMORY**

To test spatial learning and memory, *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant and control mice were studied using the Morris Water Maze test (MWM), which is known to depend on the integrity of hippocampal wiring. All mice were trained to find the platform one day before the formal MWM assay, and were then tested for three consecutive days. The average latency to find the platform was 100 ± 6.2786 s in the control group, and 130 ± 8.7563 s for the mutant group, a very significant increase (**Fig. 3A**). We also used the Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) assay to detect anxiety-related

behaviors. Mice were placed at the junction of the four arms, facing the open arm opposite to the experimenter. Their behavior was recorded for 5 min, and the ratio of the time spent in open and closed arms was calculated as described in Methods ²⁵. Whereas control mice preferred to stay in the closed arms, the *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice moved actively in the four arms, and stayed relatively longer in open arms (**Fig. 3B**). Mutant mice also explored the edges of the open arms more frequently than control animals (**Fig. 3C**). These data suggest that *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice have impaired learning and memory and are less anxiety-prone than control mice.

DISCUSSION

Selective inactivation of atypical cadherin *Celsr3* in hippocampal projection neurons results in defective hippocampal intrinsic wiring. This leads to defective hippocampal function, as indicated by impaired learning and memory, and a reduced sensitivity to anxiety. Insofar as *Emx1-Cre* expression is restricted to projection neurons, the *Celsr3|Emx1* model is different and complementary to previously studied *Celsr3|Foxg1* mice in which the target gene is inactivated in all forebrain, and *Celsr3|Dlx* mice in which *Celsr3* is inactivated in basal telencephalon and cortical, including hippocampal interneurons, but not in projection neurons ². In comparison with the two models mentioned above, the architectonics of the HF in *Celsr3|Emx1* is less severely affected, which is probably due to preservation of entorhinal afferents that are fully defective in *Celsr3|Foxg1* mice and severely affected in *Celsr3/Dlx* mutants, but preserved in *Celsr3|Emx1* mice.

Celsr3|Emx1 mice do perform poorly in the MWM test. They are able to swim normally, indicating that this poor performance is not due to motor problems resulting from the absence of CST. Inasmuch as normal hippocampal connections are requisite for learning and memory and are thus probed by the MWM assay, this defect in *Celsr3|Emx1* mice is in line with the hodological anomalies. The observation that *Celsr3|Emx1* mice are less anxiety-prone than their control littermates is more intriguing, insofar as increased anxiety is described in mouse transgenic models with decreased hippocampal volume ^{26, 27}. Another possibility would be that poor cognitive performance and defective learning and memory may lead to a decreased fear reaction in the test that we used. Indeed, such a decreased anxiety reaction has been observed in some mutant models. It is described in *Dab1* mutant mice which have a drastic architectonic alteration in the cortex and hippocampus ²⁸. A similar association of impaired cognitive function and reduced anxiety-related behavior associated to defective hippocampal function was described in mice mutant for PML ²⁹. These observations clearly show that the relationship between anxiety-related behavior and the hippocampus is not a simple one.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, *Celsr3|Emx1* mutant mice provide a simple way to study the consequences of defective hippocampal wiring in absence of drastic structural anomalies of the hippocampal formation. This model may prove useful to studies of mechanisms of diseases related to hippocampal dysfunction.

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